

Combating gender stereotypes by highlighting women's contribution to the history of societies

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HerStory Pilot Implementation

HerStory map excursion guidelines for Lecco (Italy)

WP2 D2.2

cooperativa sociale onlus

Amendment History

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1. Introduction

The current document is developed to provide guidelines on tour excursion development, for monuments of women in local history and to ensure that the experience is educational, engaging, and respectful, a set of best approaches is presented below, to select the most suitable for each country.

The first phase of excursion will take place at a pilot phase with 160 persons in total (at least in the pilot excursion), so **20 people from each country**, and at least half of the total (**10**) **must be Young people**. Following to the excursion, all partners will collect the feedback, make the necessary changes, and then prepare another excursión, the final one.

Final excursion will involve 160 persons in total (at least in the excursion), so **20 people from each country**, and least half of the total (**10**) **must be Young people**. At the end a total of 320 participants (as a minimum), at least half of the total (160) must be young people.

The participants of the excursions will consist of young people and educators, trainers and academics:

- young people, boys, and girls
- young people active in local community groups such as Municipalities' Youth Councils
- students from the fields of History
- students from the fields of Gender Studies
- youth experts
- youth organizations
- Academics from the fields of History and Gender Studies
- Teachers and educators
- Teachers, and women and human rights organizations experts/activists

Each partner will create different and specific activities for the excursions organized in their city, for the pilots and the final ones. A set of general guidelines are presented below and each partner will analyse and formulate the topics of the guidelines with additions in the excursion descriptions, based on each country specifics.

The target audience for the tour guide guidelines is:

- A. touristic offices and educators.
- B. Small groups (independent excursions)

2. Guidelines to develop a physical excursion

LEVEL 1: How to create a unique tour.

1. Define Objectives:

General Objective:

To make visible the "footprints" of some women, present and past in the area, who through their actions, their determination, their personality, their professionalism, have contributed and continue to contribute every day to defining History.

Specific objectives:

- Promote a knowledge of some historical women of the area.
- Collect the footprints of some women in a map of the territory of Lecco and Valle San Martino
- Promote an interest in local female figures in the community.
- Give value to the daily actions, to the determination and tenacity of some of the women present who have been able to affirm themselves, their ideas, their dreams.
- Offer the younger generations positive role models, examples of paths taken, goals achieved and challenges overcome.
- Promote the theme of women's value in a positive way, valuing what has been done.

2. Define the thematic of the excursion:

Tours will be led by at least one guide. To facilitate the creation of spaces for dialogue and discussion during the tour, numerically limited groups (about 20 people) will be formed. The students of the L. Rota Institute of Higher Education in Calolziocorte will be primarily involved who, since the initial phase of this project, have shown a deep interest in the issues addressed and, specifically, in the knowledge of the women present in the area involved in the project. Alongside them, different profiles will be involved, including professionals who deal with education and training.

The presence of games, in the different stages of the tour, is an element of motivation, stimulates attention and passage to all the stages. At each stop, the guide will ask the group a question; the group will have to work on finding the correct answer before proceeding to the next point on the map. Initially, this dynamic will use digital question-based gaming platforms, allowing for online interaction via mobile devices (optional for tours not moderated directly by the SM team). Alternatively, it can also be conducted using the HerStory app or without technology if internet connectivity and mobile devices are not available.

At the end of the tour, each participant will be asked to fill out a questionnaire, in which to express their opinion on the experience.

3. Recommend a rich educational content for each woman presented:

All this information is detailed in point 5 of the document.

4. Define a compelling excursion tour content:

During the tour, some specific materials of the HerStory Project will be used. Among these, at an initial stage, the tour presentation flyer is shown to the participants, in which the objectives, methods and approach used in defining the stages of the tour are explained. In addition to this, photos of the women they will meet in the various stages will be shared, videos with the interviews that each of them has released, promotional material made by the students of the L. Rota Institute of Higher Education in Calolziocorte.

5. Tour Excursion Planning:

1.

City, Country: Lecco, Italy

Tour Point: COMUNE DI MONTE MARENZO; Piazza Municipale, 5, 23804 Monte Marenzo LC; 45.77117277647121, 9.454672606595363

Subject: **PAOLA COLOMBO**

Photo:

Information:

PAOLA COLOMBO. Stakeholder of HerStory, a woman of Lecco present. Paola is mayor of the town where she lives, Monte Marenzo, where she has been serving the community for about 9 years. She enjoys gaining new experiences; at the age of 16 she spent some time studying abroad, in the United States. She likes dealing with people, building something new, she gets excited about ideas where she counts. She believes in the importance of travel, experiences and studies. She has many ideas, but she also likes to observe the ideas of others and see what can be useful in her own area. It is important for her to have people she trusts to advise her, but when she is convinced of what she believes in, she goes all the way. What does she suggest to young women? To be determined, to never stop but, at the same time, not to be in a hurry; to know how to seize opportunities, to try because you can go back and, if you don't succeed, it's not a failure, but "you can always start again from there".

Game:

Where did Paola Colombo spend her time studying abroad?

- A. In Australia
- B. In London
- C. In Spain
- D. In the U.S.

2.

City, Country: Lecco, Italy

Tour Point: ISTITUTO D'ISTRUZIONE SUPERIORE LORENZO ROTA; Via Lavello, 17, 23801 Calolziocorte LC; 45.79360578710849, 9.432719593829129

Subject: **STUDENTS**

Photo:

Information:

BOYS and GIRLS from the Lorenzo Rota Higher Education Institute. Active protagonists of HerStory, they shared reflections, ideas, knowledge, desires, aspirations with respect to the topic of gender. They recognise the value of practical example, of their adult role models, of a story that looks not only to the past but also and above all to the present; a story that is capable of leaving imprints today for the future. Directly involved in project activities, they will be the drivers of a new focus on the topic.

Game:

What did the young men and women of the Rota Institute do within HerStory?

- A. They shared reflections, ideas, knowledge, desires, aspirations with respect to the theme of gender
- B. Nothing
- C. They got to know their European partners
- D. They wrote lyrics

3.

City, Country: Lecco, Italy

Tour Point: L'ISOLA DELLA STUPIDERA: Via Ca' Romano, 23854 Olginate LC;
45.780432166469474, 9.426251366845603

Subject: **ALESSANDRA MAGGI**

Photo:

Information:

ALESSANDRA MAGGI. Stakeholder of HerStory, woman of Lecco present. Alessandra describes herself as a teacher by choice. After graduating in Primary Education, she obtained a Master's degree in Clinical Pedagogy. She is the president of “L'isola della Stupidera”, a social promotion association that takes care of meeting and entertainment spaces for families. It is a reality born from her desire to create a “time within my happy everyday life” that was always thought out and made to measure. She likes to be inside contexts, to observe and understand what is needed without too many methods and structures. She believes in the importance of having more male figures at school, to give children the opportunity to recognise their own gender and the opposite. What does she suggest to young women? To do what they like and involve others; generate something that makes them feel good; recognise their need and make it everyone's need.

Game:

What does Alessandra Maggi think is useful to be more in schools?

- A. More hours dedicated to art
- B. More hours dedicated to English
- C. A greater presence of male figures
- D. A greater presence of young people

4.

City, Country: Lecco, Italy

Tour Point: COMUNE DI OLGINATE; Piazza Volontari del Sangue, 1, 23854 Olginate LC;
45.79928734702603, 9.412264871605338

Subject: **MARINA CALEGARI**

Photo:

Information:

MARINA CALEGARI. Stakeholder of HerStory, a woman of Lecco present. Marina is an architect, interested in the world of construction since she was a child. She is also a sports enthusiast and has practised skiing and water skiing at a competitive level, travelling extensively. She studied architecture at the Milan Polytechnic. In recent years, she has also dedicated herself to the political life of her town, Olginate, as municipal councillor, and as vice-mayor. She is currently councillor for social, sport and

youth policies and councillor in the “Comunità Montana”. She has worked as a volunteer in the Lions Club and is currently on the board of “Impresa sociale Girasole”. She is very passionate about working as a public administrator: it is for her the way to give back to the community what she has received. She believes in the importance of equal opportunities, respect and the value of individuality. What does she suggest to young women? To believe, to be reliable and tenacious; to be responsible, empathetic and listening. Try to involve, work as a team, be a team player.

Game:

What does Marina suggest to young women?

- A. To play sports
- B. To get involved in politics
- C. To be reliable and tenacious
- D. Not to listen to others

5.

City, Country: Lecco, Italy

Tour Point: LIONS LECCO: Via Maggiore, 19, 23900 Lecco LC; 45.844912114864435,
9.398766311031418

Soggetto: **MARINA BALOSI**

Photo:

Information:

MARINA BALOSSI. Stakeholder of HerStory, a woman of Lecco present. Marina is an entrepreneur and coordinator of the “Lions New Voices Committee”. Her daughters help define who she is today; having walked with them "determines me". She has an optimistic approach to the future: her family taught her that you don't give up, you don't give in, and that you always need courage; she also looks ahead with a sense of humour and her self-deprecation helps her in this. She believes in the importance of taking space and making an impact in practice, focusing less on big laws or impositions, but making an impact in the here and now. What does she suggest to young women? Not to live subject to the judgement of others, not to always conform, to be listening, to value the encounters they make in their own story, because every encounter is capable of leaving a mark and allows you to leave your own mark.

Game:

What does Marina suggest to young women?

- A. To take your time
- B. Not to live subject to the judgment of others
- C. To go on trips
- D. To write and document

6.

City, Country: Lecco, Italy

Tour Point: SEDE SOCIALE "HOTEL NH PONTEVECCHIO" di Lecco. Via Azzone Visconti, 84, 23900 Lecco LC. 45.848797445469074, 9.392827710482996

Subject: **FULVIA GREPPI**

Photo:

Information:

FULVIA GREPPI. Stakeholder of HerStory, woman of Lecco present. Fulvia is an entrepreneur. For the past three years she has been working in the association “Compagnia delle Opere”, which aims to support entrepreneurs, non-profit organisations, managers and professionals in the development of businesses and professional activities in an orientation for the good of all. She also likes to contribute to the social, national and international dimension; that is why she is a member of 'Soroptimist', an organisation that promotes actions and creates opportunities through the global network of members and international cooperation, so that all women can realise their individual and collective potential, realise their aspirations and create strong peaceful communities in the world. As an entrepreneur, she believes in work as a passion, as a relational life experience. Travelling opened her mind to the condition of women, which she then found in some realities in her area. What does she suggest to young women? To be consistent with themselves, to value independence and curiosity; to be flexible and resilient with respect to the physiological criticalities they will encounter. Travelling and learning are useful tools to confront and better understand that rights are not taken for granted, that what we have needs constant affirmation; to know how to oppose and not accept the first signs of discrimination.

Game:

What is Fulvia's job?

- A. She is a primary school teacher
- B. She's a doula
- C. She is an entrepreneur
- D. She's an actress

7.

City, Country: Lecco, Italy

Tour Point: LECCO POLICE HEADQUARTERS. Corso Promessi Sposi, 40, 23900 Lecco LC.
45.85531353440556, 9.403488536978456

Subject: **LUISA BONO**

Photo:

Information:

LUISA BONO. Stakeholder of HerStory, a woman of Lecco present. Luisa is a psychologist and psychotherapist. She graduated in Developmental Psychology and Educational Processes at Milano-Bicocca University and specialised in cognitive-behavioural-oriented psychotherapy at the Studi Cognitivi school in Milan. For several years she has been working in the field of primary prevention of child sexual abuse; she is an auxiliary of the Judicial Police and she works in the assessment and care of

minors in situations of abuse and maltreatment. She believes in the importance of education and prevention from an early age; developing critical thinking, good examples, good role models. What does she suggest to young women? To be determined, despite hardships, to be tenacious, to be committed; to create a good synergy together, to stick together. Find the right way to manage one's time, give everything its due, give everything its weight, including taking personal space.

Game:

What does Luisa do?

- A. Psychotherapy
- B. Primary prevention of child abuse and maltreatment
- C. Hearing of minors for the Judicial Police
- D. All of the above

8.

City, Country: Lecco, Italy

Tour Point: Via Cadorna, Lecco, LC, 23900; 45.858920055345244, 9.385407411032437

Soggetto: **LEA GAROFALO**

Photo:

Information:

LEA GAROFALO. In 2020, an associative reality in Lecco promoted an innovative action: symbolically changing the names of three city streets, naming them after great women

of Italian history. Through a poll, citizens chose three women: among them, LEA GAROFALO. Lea was born in 1974 in Petilia Policastro (Crotone) where she grew up in a “Ndrangheta’s” family. She soon developed a spontaneous and genuine opposition to crime, trafficking and the logic that also belonged to her family, and so in 2002 she testified about the internal feuds between her family and that of her former partner Carlo Cosco. Initially subjected to protection, she was then excluded from the programme and, once readmitted, continued to be considered a collaborator of justice and not a witness; a condition that Lea did not accept. Threatened several times, in 2009 she was killed by her former partner and her body was set on fire.

Link extra: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YtzArWI-Fcg>

Game:

What region is Lea from?

- A. Lombardy
- B. Campania
- C. Calabria
- D. Veneto

9.

City, Country: Lecco, Italy

Tour Point: TEATRO SOCIALE DI LECCO. Piazza Giuseppe Garibaldi, 10, 23900 Lecco LC.
45.85292897869079, 9.389269938014593

Subject: **AURORA SPREAFICO**

Photo:

Information:

AURORA SPREAFICO. Stakeholder of HerStory, woman of Lecco present. Aurora is an actress and writer. She graduated from the Luca Ronconi School of “Piccolo Teatro di Milano” where she trained and worked with various actors and directors. In 2021, she published “Cavallucci”, her first collection of poems. Theatre is her passion and her dream; commitment and passion guide her in the pursuit of her professional and personal path. She enjoys engaging with young people who are choosing their future, offering them concrete spaces for dialogue and helping them to identify their interests and aspirations.

Link extra: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=l5rvrB3bB_I

Game:

Aurora is:

- A. Actress
- B. Writer
- C. Woman of the present from Lecco
- D. All of the above

10.

City, Country: Lecco, Italy

Tour Point: via del Rocolo, Lecco, LC, 23900; 45.850424123328374,
9.411676295686902

Subject: **FRANCESCA CICERI**

Photo:

Information:

FRANCESCA CICERI. In 2020, an associative reality in Lecco promoted an innovative action: symbolically changing the names of three city streets, naming them after great women of Italian history. Through a poll, citizens chose three women: among them, FRANCESCA CICERI. Francesca was born in Lecco in 1904; a member of the Communist Party of Italy, she was particularly active in organising and leading Italian women's groups in Paris and Lyon. She then returned to Italy to carry out anti-fascist activities among the textile workers and to direct the struggle of the "mondine" (rice weeders); having escaped and returned to Italy clandestinely from the Leninist school in Mosca, she and her husband were arrested and sentenced to eight years imprisonment. In 1943, she and her husband went to the Piani d'Erna and formed one of the first partisan formations. After the Liberation, she became leader of the PCI women's federation and a member of the Women's Consultative Commission of the Milan Chamber of Labour. In the last years of her life, she was president of the Lecco ANPI. In 1977, the municipal administration awarded her the gold medal for the Resistance. She died in Lecco in 1988.

Game:

Why did the municipal administration award Francesca the gold medal?

- A. For Medical Research
- B. For the Resistance**
- C. For social research
- D. For his artistic contributions

11.

City, Country: Lecco, Italy

Tour Point: CENTRO CIVICO SANDRO PERTINI; 23900 Lecco LC; 45.852224154222895,
9.413542911031952

Subject: **MARIA CALVETTI**

Photo:

Information:

MARIA CALVETTI. On International Women's Day (2023), the Sandro Pertini Civic Centre (Lecco) was named after her. Maria was born in Lecco in 1950. Together with her husband, she set up the "Open Families" group of the "Centro Orientamento Educativo" (COE). She was president of the "Associazione Lecchese Famiglie Affidatarie" (Lecco Association of Foster Families) until obtaining, in 2011, together with her husband, the civic merit of the Municipality of Lecco for their testimony of a

lifestyle marked by the values of concrete solidarity and openness to the world. She passed away in 2018.

Game:

Which place was named after Maria Calvetti?

- A. Hospital of Lecco
- B. Sandro Pertini Civic Centre in Lecco
- C. Teatro della Società di Lecco
- D. A square in Lecco

12.

City, Country: Lecco, Italy

Tour Point: AMBITO DISTRETTUALE DI LECCO. Via Graziano Tubi, 43, 23900 Lecco LC.
45.85530887384826, 9.401667630961006

Subject: **ROMINA PAPINI**

Photo:

Information:

ROMINA PAPINI. Stakeholder of HerStory, a woman of Lecco present. Romina is a pedagogist, a professional educator and a doula. She provides “gentle” support to new parents, supporting them both in the practical management of the tasks related to

pregnancy and the newborn child and in the psychological dimension; it is therefore an accompaniment at different levels, in which “being gentle” is, for her, the key. She likes working in a network with municipalities, families, and health institutions, and she is now a point of reference at provincial level for the maternal-infant sphere, in pre-natal care. Today she is happy to have realised her dream: to work within the public service, therefore dedicated to everyone. Being a mother has helped her to understand how much you must be light when working with mothers and fathers; sometimes you just have to be. Her mantra is “walk light because you walk on my dreams”. What does she suggest to young women? To be tenacious, to try hard when they believe in something; to talk, discuss and share.

Game:

In which area is Romina a reference today?

- A. Local associations
- B. Administration of the Municipality in which you reside
- C. Provincial maternal and child care
- D. School environment

13.

City, Country: Lecco, Italy

Tour Point: SALA CIVICA A SAN GIOVANNI; Via Don Luigi Orione, 8, 23900 Lecco LC;

45.86670185833263, 9.407538309179346

Subject: **CARLA FERRACINI**

Photo:

Information:

CARLA FERRACINI. On International Women's Day (2023), the civic hall in San Giovanni (Lecco) was named after her. Carla was born in Lecco in 1932. She attended the Brera Academy of Fine Arts in Brera and Milan and courses in Xylography and Lithography in Urbino. On returning to her hometown, she devoted herself to teaching, without however abandoning her artistic career. Two exhibitions were dedicated to her in Lecco: the first in 1998 at the Torre Viscontea and the second in 2012, again in the Torre Viscontea, entitled "Vie d'uscita". She donated one of her works to the "Sistema Museale Urbano Lecchese": "Il vascello fantasma". In 2001, Carla created the monument for Aido installed at Castello Cemetery. She passed away in February 2022.

Game:

Where did Carla study art?

- A. Academy of Fine Arts of Florence
- B. **Brera Academy of Fine Arts**
- C. Academy of Fine Arts of Venice
- D. Academy of Fine Arts of Naples

14.

City, Country: Lecco, Italy

Tour Point: SALA CIVICA DI CASTELLO; Via Seminario, 39, 23900 Lecco LC;
45.864297092066586, 9.394507353360378

Subject: **GABRIELLA MALGARINI ZANINI**

Photo:

Information:

GABRIELLA MALGARINI ZANINI. On International Women's Day (2023), the civic hall in Castello (Lecco) was named after her. Gabriella was born in Mantova in 1921 and later moved to Lecco together with her husband, who like her was a paediatrician. Scarred by her father's death, she was interested from the outset in the study of palliative care, which began to be discussed in Lecco in 1995, when she proposed a service to the Soroptimist Club aimed at terminally ill oncological patients. In October 1996, the ACMT, "Associazione per la Cura dei Malati Terminali" (Association for the Care of the Terminally Ill) was established, of which she was president and with which she signed an agreement in 1999 to collaborate with the Asl home care service. Appointed honorary president in 2007, she passed away in 2010.

Game:

What was Gabriella's job?

- A. Teaching

- B. Cure Palliative
- C. Architecture
- D. Entrepreneurship

15.

City, Country: Lecco, Italy

Tour Point: via Bersaglio, Lecco, LC, 23900; 45.86441445137566, 9.392062226377785

Subject: **NILDE IOTTI**

Photo:

Information:

NILDE IOTTI. In 2020, an associative reality in Lecco promoted an innovative action: symbolically changing the names of three city streets, naming them after great women of Italian history. Through a poll, citizens chose three women: among them, NILDE LIOTTI. Nilde was born in 1920 in Reggio Emilia, graduated in literature from the Catholic University of Milan; she directed the Women's Defence Group, a structure that was very active in the war of Liberation. She was the promoter of the family law (1975), the battle on the divorce referendum (1974) and the abortion law (1978). She was the first woman in the history of republican Italy to hold the office of President of the Chamber of Deputies; she went on to chair the Parliamentary Commission for Institutional Reforms and was elected Vice-President of the Council of Europe. The 'Lady of the Republic' passed away in 1999.

Link extra:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=okiugC3fvIk>

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=34rbBJT6Y_8

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eQDVLYXL4p0>

Game:

Which of these positions has Nilde Iotti held?

- A. President of the Chamber of Deputies
- B. Chairmanship of the Parliamentary Committee
- C. Vice-President of the Council of Europe
- D. All of the above

LEVEL 2: How to implement an exciting tour.

1. Add Interactive Elements to excursion tour:

If the mobile app being developed through the HerStory project is ready for use during the pilot phase of the tour, it will be implemented. For the time being, we will rely on the part of the Quiz defined above and the supporting audiovisual material.

2. Verify accessibility and provide necessary information:

Any specific needs of people with reduced mobility or older age will be taken into account.

As far as cultural sensitivity is concerned, sensitive information is not initially discussed on the planned tour. Finally, members of the Magic Mirror team who can moderate tours are also able to communicate in English in case someone doesn't have a strong command of Italian.

3. Receive Feedback and Improvement:

Ai partecipanti ai tour sarà richiesto di rispondere al questionario dopo aver completato l'attività. Inizialmente, verrà utilizzato il questionario dell'Unione europea (UE). Oltre a questa raccolta, il team Specchio Magico registrerà alcuni indicatori associati al coinvolgimento e alla soddisfazione espressa in merito al completamento dell'attività. Alla fine di questa osservazione, ai partecipanti verrà chiesto se hanno proposte di miglioramento, commenti, dubbi da includere o questioni da sollevare in merito all'attività.

La raccolta dei dati per il questionario UE avverrà al termine della caccia al tesoro al punto 11.

4. Engage Locals through Collaborations:

Collaborate with local historians, institutes, experts, or community leaders who can provide insights into the historical and cultural context of each monument. Moreover, consider involving local women's groups or organizations in the planning and execution of the tour. Conduct research, to see if there are other events dedicated to women on the local monuments, that can be linked to the excursion tour.

The engagement of the Rota Institute of Higher Education, its 800 students, teachers and educators is a multiplier element. The group of boys and girls hired in the implementation

phase will carry out, within the institute, specific communication and dissemination actions of the project products and the HerStory Map.

In addition to these, among the potential collaborators there are the operators of the Specchio Magico cooperative, who carry out educational, sports and leisure projects within the territory with young people between 6 and 14 years old.

LEVEL 3: Generic guidelines for individual and self-guided tours.

1. Enable the customization of excursions:

The pilot projects of the tour are scheduled between April and June 2024, with the collaboration of the L. Rota Institute of Higher Education in Calolziocorte, to promote the initiative. This activity aims to discover the significant contributions made by women in the city. As for the final visits of the project, they can be organized on different key dates (specific anniversaries) or with the active involvement of the stakeholders, who constitute the Women of the Present of the HerStory Map.

2. Develop options for Training Guides or/and self-guided tours:

To make sure that the HerStory Map is not just a list of stops and women, but becomes an experience in which the visitor is engaged and involved, we are organizing a tour in the form of a treasure hunt.

The dynamics of the tour involve dividing the participants into several groups, each led by a Magic Mirror operator. All groups will ride the same route, which includes 15 key points throughout the city. Given the distance between some points, the tour can be done over several days and the transfers involve both the use of private cars/public transport, and the movement on foot. To facilitate such travel, potential places of departure and arrival are provided.

The primary objective is to make known some women, past and present, who have left or leave significant marks in the history of our territory.

At each stage, participants will have the opportunity to meet a woman, and have fun in an inherent quiz. Before proceeding to the next location on the map, the guide will submit a question. After providing the correct answer, the guide will provide insights into the current landmark, advancing the group to the next point. This methodology aims to promote the awareness of prominent women from different perspectives, amalgamating elements of gamification with collaborative engagement.

In the case of a self-guided visit, the following recommendations can be adopted:

- **Educate yourself:** Conduct research into the history of various prominent women associated with the city of Sofia. This includes understanding both the times in which they lived and their contributions, achievements, and significance in various fields such as politics, the arts, sciences, and social activism.
- **Create an informational flyer.** Collect in a booklet the stages of the tour and some key information about the Women you will meet at each point. Develop an information document, such as a brochure, outlining the 11 points of interest in Salamanca associated with women who have contributed to the city. This material should include descriptive information regarding each woman and their respective position in the city.
- **Create an interactive questionnaire** on an online platform allowing participants to feel active and engaged during the self-guided tour. This questionnaire should include questions related to the history of eminent women and the places visited, using the existing questionnaire as a template.
- **Establish the two potential starting and finishing points** for the self-guided tour and the intermediate stops (follow a specific logic: proximity of the points, period in which that woman lived/lives, area of expertise,...)
- **Encourage exploration.** Motivate participants to explore beyond the designated tour route and discover other sites and stories related to prominent women in the area. Provide suggestions for further exploration and discovery.
- **Share additional resources** to increase knowledge and stimulate interest. Provide attendees with resources to continue learning about the women on the tour, such as recommended readings, events, and local exhibits.

Extra tips.

Having a QRCode printed to go to the local map of the city, so people can follow the tour or access to the guidelines to make the tour in an educational way.

2. Documentation and templates

The deliverables of WP4 activities are presented below:

D4.1 HERSTORY MAP pilot implementation

- **Invitation/ agenda/ program:** A template will be shared by KEAN.
- **Signed attendance list**
- **Mintes/ report (tbd)**
- **Other evidence** (in case of pictures we need consent forms)